

Songrium: Browsing and Listening Environment for Music Content Creation Community

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a music browsing assistance service, *Songrium* (<http://songrium.jp>) that enables visualization and exploration of massive user-generated music content with the aim of enhancing user experiences in enjoying music. Such massive user-generated content has yielded “*web-native music*”, which we defined as musical pieces that are published, shared, and remixed (have derivative works created) entirely on the web. *Songrium* has two interfaces for browsing and listening to web-native music from the viewpoints of scale and time: *Songrium3D* for gaining community-scale awareness and *Interactive History Player* for gaining community-history awareness. Both of them were developed to stimulate community activities for web-native music by visualizing massive music content spatially or chronologically and by providing interactive enriched experiences. *Songrium* has analyzed over 680,000 music video clips on the most popular Japanese video-sharing service, *Niconico*, which includes original songs of web-native music and their derivative works such as covers and dance arrangements. Analyses of more than 120,000 original songs reveal that over 560,000 derivative works have been generated and contributed to enriching massive user-generated music content.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since many amateur musicians started releasing their new original songs on video sharing services, a new type of music content that is born, listened to, and distributed on the web becomes popular. Many derivative works, such as cover versions and music video clips of those songs, have also been actively created and shared by other creators. Such music content is called *web-native music* [1] and has ever been increasing. This is different from commercially distributed songs that are originally released on the market and then copied to video sharing services.

Creators and listeners of web-native music form an interesting community that grows up and keeps on updating its own history dynamically on the web. This dynamics makes it difficult for people to grasp the whole picture of the community. Although ranking and recommendation are pow-

A) Songrium3D: Scale-aware visualization

B) Interactive History Player: Time-aware visualization

Figure 1. Songrium3D and Interactive History Player. The former is scale-aware visualization and the latter is time-aware visualization for music content creation community.

erful and typical ways to find popular and similar music content in usual, they are not effective enough to grasp the whole picture. The goal of this research is to enable people to efficiently browse and listen to web-native music while grasping its nature and history.

In this paper we therefore propose to extend our web service called *Songrium* (<http://songrium.jp>) [1, 2]¹ by adding two interfaces, *Songrium3D* and *Interactive History Player*, that help people to be aware of the scale and history of the music content creation community through visualizing music content. *Songrium3D* visualizes the whole content in three dimensional space to gain

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¹A demonstration video of Songrium is available at <https://staff.aist.go.jp/masahiro.hamasaki/SMC2015/>.

community-scale awareness (Figure 1-A). Interactive History Player visualizes the whole content chronologically to gain community-history awareness (Figure 1-B). The current target content of Songrium is original songs using the singing synthesis technology *VOCALOID* [3] and their derivative works on Nico Nico, the most popular Japanese video-sharing service.

Songrium3D visualizes original songs as if they are stars in a planetarium.. Their positions are automatically arranged so that songs with similar moods can be closely located and be easily listened to by the user. Also, it seamlessly visualizes overviews of the whole content and details of each content. Furthermore, Songrium3D shows automatically synthesized visual effects for each user-generated music content during music playback. The effects are composed of predefined elements and their compositions are based on the analysis of music structure, both contributing to the high quality visuals.

Interactive History Player exhibits the growth in popularity of songs, arranged by published date, in an animated display. This feature enables users to experience a group of songs in one continuous movie, providing a clear, intuitive picture of how trends on video-sharing services have changed.

We launched Songrium in August 2012 and over 147,000 users have used our service. Since more than 120,000 original songs and 560,000 derivative works have already been registered and new songs are also automatically registered every day, Songrium is the only large-scale web service that can provide a comprehensive overview of the music content creation community for *VOCALOID*.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 explains music content creation community within the *VOCALOID* community on Nico Nico. Section 3 introduces basic functions provided by Songrium. Section 4 describes Songrium3D and Section 5 describes Interactive History Player. Section 6 presents our experiences with Songrium and Section 7 summarizes this paper's contributions.

2. WEB-NATIVE MUSIC ON NICONICO

Nico Nico is an extremely popular video communication service in Japan today. As with similar services (YouTube, etc.), users are able to upload and view videos. User-generated music content is the subject of many videos. Among them, music contents related to *VOCALOID* are popular, and are different from the rest as explained below.

VOCALOID is a singing synthesis technology [3] that forms a subset of the music content creation community on Nico Nico. This technology is used to synthesize the main vocal melody of songs. Many examples have been published as original works on the website. Despite the impressive technology used for the songs, the vocals produced by *VOCALOID* are readily identifiable as not of human origin, meaning that both creators and listeners naturally accept that these songs are first published on the web. Nico Nico therefore serves as a forum for *VOCALOID* creators and listeners to gather and share their relations.

Many different products are based on *VOCALOID*; each has a different vocal timbre. Most products have an associ-

Figure 2. Two top graphs shows that the total number of published original songs and their derivative works in the period September 2007 – December 2014. The two bottom graphs shows the monthly number of published original songs and their derivative works in 2014.

ated character image, with Hatsune Miku ² being the most well-known. Soon after releasing Hatsune Miku, Crypton Future Media (the developer of Hatsune Miku) officially started allowing users to reuse its character for derivative works with their original license: Piapro Character License ³. Subsequently, users started to create music videos, such as promotion videos for musicians, with such original songs and drawings. Some users even went so far as to create 3D models of Hatsune Miku and create 3D animation videos [4, 5]. Thereafter, many songwriters published karaoke (full song without vocals) versions of their own original songs, prompting some users to sing these songs and to publish derivative works recorded in video clips.

We designated music having such characteristics as *web-native music* [1] and defined the conditions of web-native music as shown below.

- (1) It is generally assumed that new original songs are first released on the web (without CD release or radio play, for example), with a unique URL identifying the source and release date.
- (2) Creators do not hesitate to create and release derivative works of original songs on the web.
- (3) After releasing original or derivative works, their creators can publicly receive feedback on the web and be encouraged to create more related materials.

Under the conditions mentioned above, web-native music naturally encourages to create derivative work. In fact, many derivative works are uploaded on Nico Nico. Figure 2 shows the number of total published original songs and their derivative works from September 2007 through December 2014 and the number of monthly published items in 2014. As described herein, we define the term ‘derivative work’ as a video clip that reuses a part of or whole of

² http://www.crypton.co.jp/mp/pages/prod/vocaloid/cv01_us.jsp

³ From December 2012, they use Creative Commons license for foreign users.

Figure 3. Distribution of time spans between publishing dates of original songs and their derivative works.

video clip of VOCALOID original song. According to this figure, the number of uploaded original songs and derivative works has been increasing rapidly. In 2014, about 1,500 original songs and 7,000 derivative works were published month by month.

Figure 3 depicts the distribution of time spans of publishing dates between an original song and its derivative works. Actually, 80% of derivative works are published after one month of the original publication date, whereas 40% are published after one year, showing that derivative works extend the longevity of original works. Furthermore, 14% of original songs have a derivative work with page views higher than original work, indicating that derivative works are also attractive contents.

3. SONGRIMUM

3.1 Overview

Songrium is a music browsing assistance service that facilitates the understanding of the massive user-generated music content within the VOCALOID community on the Niconico service. Figure 4 presents an overview of Songrium. Songrium automatically gathers information related to original songs and their derivative works that grow day after day. It then classifies these contents and estimates the relations between original songs and derivative works. Songrium visualizes using results of music understanding.

By visualizing the web-native music, Songrium improves a user’s understanding of various relations in the web-native music and an enriched interactive experience with the Web of Music. It was difficult for people listening to original songs to notice that there exist various derivative works of them, such as cover versions, singing or dancing video clips, and music video clips with 3D animations. By providing people with easy, intuitive access to those derivative works, Songrium enables them not only to find interesting music video clips but also to understand and respect the creators of music and video clips.

Songrium uses web mining and music understanding technologies together with advanced data visualization techniques to achieve unique function, such as a Music Star

Figure 4. System overview of Songrium.

Map, Songrium3D (in Section 4), and Interactive History Player (in Section 5).

3.2 Web mining of Songrium

Every music video clip on Songrium is classified automatically as an original song or a derivative work. Niconico supports social tags for each clip and tags of some kinds such as “Original Song” and “be enshrined in the Hall of Fame song” are usually put on original songs on Niconico. Therefore, these tags are reliable. However, even if some original songs have no such tag, Songrium automatically classifies them correctly by crawling a set of related web sites to generate the “white list” of VOCALOID original songs. In the case of derivative works, these can be readily identified when the description text of the video clip includes a hyperlink to the original video clip from which it was derived. These hyperlinks almost always exist on Niconico because users like to acknowledge the original video clip.

When a derivative work is incorporated, its relation to the original song is estimated automatically. The derivative works are classified into the predefined categories. We defined six categories of derivative works: (a) Singing a song, (b) Dancing to a song, (c) Performing a song on musical instruments, (d) Featuring 3D characters in music video, (e) Creating a music video for a song, and (f) Others. The first three categories are derived from official categories used by Niconico; the other two categories are derived from our previous work [4, 5]. “Others” includes, for example, videos which review or rank existing videos, or which use VOCALOID songs as the background music to other video contents. With the exception of category *Others* all the remaining categories are extremely popular. All have their own unique social tags on Niconico. Using these tags, Songrium can produce a reliable classification of derivative works. Table 1 presents classification results of 564,623 derivative works of 128,044 VOCALOID original songs that we gathered from Niconico.

Table 1. Classification results of 564,623 derivative works. Some derivative works have multiple categories. Therefore, the total number of classifications is greater than the number of derivative works.

category	# of works
(a) Singing	379,342
(b) Dancing	30,159
(c) Arranging and Performing	35,584
(d) Featuring 3D characters	33,270
(e) Creating Music video	9,062
(f) Others	84,137

Moreover, Songrium enables users to report an error in any of the above classification of video clips, extraction of links, or estimation of relations easily to improve the user experience further.

3.3 Visualization of Songrium

Songrium has various functions of visualization for music content [2] [1]. *Music Star Map* is a function that visualizes original songs. Original songs are embedded in a two-dimensional space, mapped automatically based on audio feature similarity. The position of a song on the map is such that songs in proximity have similar moods (estimated by audio feature analysis). Figure 5-(A) portrays a screenshot of this function. Furthermore, when a user clicks an original song on Music Star Map, its derivative works appear as colorful icons and orbit the selected song. We designate this view as the “Planet View.” Figure 5-(B) presents a Planet View screenshot.

In Figure 5-(B), each circle icon denotes a derivative work with attributes represented by the icon orbit, size, color, and velocity. The distance from the center is indicative of the publishing date, with the most recent work in the outermost orbit. The size of each icon reflects the number of page views; the color indicates one of the following derivative categories: Blue (Singing), Red (Dancing), Green (Arranging and Performing), Purple (3D characters in music video), Yellow (Creating music video), and White (Others). Finally, the velocity (orbit speed) of an icon represents how many times the content has been favorited by users of the system.

The official embedded video player of the Niconico service, shown at the upper-right corner, can play back a video clip of the selected original song (Fig. 5-(C)). Our music-listening interface has a chorus-search function for trial listening, *SmartMusicKIOSK* [6], which is shown below the embedded player (Fig. 5-(D)). Songrium has an original social tagging framework called the ‘Arrow Tag’ that allows to annotate a relation between music content [2]. Figure 5-(E) shows a list of Arrow Tags.

4. SONGRIUM3D

Songrium3D is a novel visualization interface based on the *Music Star Map* of Songrium. The Music Star Map visualizes original songs and their derivative works in two-

Figure 6. Screenshot of the “Songrium3D”. (A) Users can search songs using keywords. Similarly, users can search playlists in Niconico using keywords or a URL. When users choose a Mylist, it starts auto play. (B) It shows a playlist. (C) This spherical object indicates an original song. Some objects and ribbons near the song are visual effects that synchronized to a song. (D) A song is encompassed with many colorful particles which mean its derivative works. (E) Other original songs can be seen way out there. (F) Embedded video player of Niconico for video playback and SmartMusicKIOSK for trial listening.

dimensional space, but Songrium3D visualizes them in three-dimensional space. Using three-dimensional visualization, Songrium3D (1) visualizes whole contents, and (2) visualize songs, derivative works, and music structure seamlessly.

Figure 6 presents screenshot of the Songrium3D. The spherical object represents an original song in the center of the figure. When it plays a song, this object and peripheral objects move rhythmically that synchronized to a song. Many colorful circumjacent materials indicate derivative works of an original song. Color means a category of derivative works in the same manner as PlanetView (Fig. 5-(B)).

In the above, we describe that Songrium3D visualizes music structure of a song, derivative works of a song, and other songs at a time. The important point is that it is not only visualizing them at once but also visualizing them seamlessly. Figure 7 shows the transition from the top page to a user-specified song. First, all original VOCALOID songs are visualized in a three-dimensional space where songs which sound similar are positioned in proximity, similar to stars in a cosmos (Fig. 7-1). The colors of these stars correspond to VOCALOID characters, with brightness indicating popularity (number of plays). When a user chooses a song, a camera starts to move to the song (Fig. 7-2). Users can gradually see more of the song and its derivative works (Fig. 7-3,4). Songrium3D depicts derivative works as planets orbiting a star (original song). The planet color corresponds to the type of derivative work (singing, dancing, musical cover etc.) It displays all derivative works of the song using massive particles.

After arriving at the song, it displays visual effects that synchronized with sounds of the song (Fig. 7-3,5). Derivative works and other songs are shown in the background

Figure 5. Screenshot of the (A) “Music Star Map” and (B) “Planet View” interface in Songrium. The former visualizes original songs; the latter visualizes their derivative works. Both are connected seamlessly. (A) All original songs are arranged in a two-dimensional space with similar songs positioned in proximity. Any particular area can be expanded for viewing by double clicking. It can then be scrolled to by dragging. (B) After selecting an original song on Music Star Map, users can view its derivative works rotating around the selected song in the center. (C) Embedded video player of NicoNico for video playback. (D) Playback interface for trial listening (SmartMusicKIOSK). (E) Social annotated relations called Arrow tags [2] to and from this song instance.

when it shows visual effects that are a visualization of music structure. In this manner, Songrium3D visualizes all contents seamlessly. That is an important benefit of three-dimensional visualization. It helps users to have awareness of greatness of this music content creation community.

Songrium3D visualizes musical facets such as the beat and phrase structure, supported by signal processing and music understanding technologies. Figure 8 presents that how Songrium3D generates visual effects that synchronized to a song. Many music players have visual effects that are synchronized to audio signals. However, in the Songrium3D, visual effects synchronized to music structure, that is chorus section and repeated sections. One visual effect is mapped to one repeated section. Songrium3D has only six patterns of visual effects, however each songs has a different music structure. Then Songrium3D can generate various visual effects synchronized to a song. Handcrafted visual effects can be reflected by the deep meaning of a song, but it is high-cost. On the other hand, a signal visualization approach is low-cost, but it can visualize only shallow meaning of a song. Our approach is a combination of handcraft and automated generation. It is middle-cost and it can be reflected by the meaning of a song.

5. INTERACTIVE HISTORY PLAYER

Interactive History Player visualizes the history of VOCALOID songs. It plays groups of associated songs published within a user-specified time frame on continuous playback. The interface exhibits the growth in popularity of songs, arranged by published date, in an animated display. It plays songs whose play count is high in the period automatically. Consequently, this feature enables

users to experience a group of songs in one continuous movie, providing a clear, intuitive picture of how trends on video-sharing services behave. If users become curious about some songs, users can play them with drag-and-drop operations.

Figure 9 portrays a screen shot of Interactive History Player. It displays groups of songs published during the specified period in chronological order, giving the user a full perspective on the trends and transitions in published song groups over time. Each song is represented by a “bubble” (a colored circle). New song bubbles appear in accordance with their respective published dates and congregate in an animation. The colors of the bubbles correspond to the voice synthesis library used in the VOCALOID software, whereas the sizes of the bubbles indicate play counts. On the left side of the screen, the bar chart presents a summation of play counts of bubbles in the same VOCALOID characters.

Users can choose a song for listening, change a period, and filter songs by VOCALOID solely by mouse operation. Furthermore, Songrium plays truncated chorus sections of certain songs that satisfy conditions specified by the user, making it easy to see what kinds of songs were being published as bubbles increasingly appear. These interactive functions help users to browse music contents.

The Interactive History Player has two different versions, “Singing derivative works” version and “Dancing derivative works” version. They display derivative works with the same interface. The bubble colors correspond to their original songs. A bar chart shows a trend of original songs for derivative works.

Figure 9. Screenshot of the “Interactive History Player” in Songrium. It visualizes the history of VOCALOID songs. (A) A bubble means music content. Its size indicates play counts and its color indicates VOCALOID. When users click a bubble, its thumbnail and metadata are shown. (B) Users drag and drop a bubble here, then the song is added to the playlist. (C) Timeline displays the current time and popular content in each period. When users click on the timeline, it jumps to the clicked period. (D) It displays groups of songs published during the specified period in chronological order, automatically. (E) Bar chart shows summation of play counts of bubbles.

6. EXPERIENCES WITH SONGRIMUM

6.1 Songrium on the Web

Users can use all functions of Songrium and can watch the latest music contents everyday merely by the web browser. The web crawler of Songrium checks updated music video clips related to VOCALOID on Nico Nico automatically on a daily basis. The user interface of Songrium is implemented using HTML5, SVG, JavaScript, the JavaScript library D3.js, threeJS, and the embedded video player of the Nico Nico service.

Songrium service was released to the public at <http://songrium.jp> on August 7, 2012. In addition to the web service, the Songrium extension for Google’s Chrome browser was released on February 28, 2013. As of April 2015, 128,044 original songs and 564,623 derivative works have been registered in Songrium. More than 147,000 users have visited our web site. More than 2,500 users have installed the browser extension.

6.2 Songrium3D on the live stage

Animation of Songrium3D was used as a back screen movie on the live stage of Hatsune Miku in the “SNOW MIKU 2015 LIVE!” held four times in February 7th-8th, 2015. It was hosted by Crypton Future Media Inc. for an audience of over 7,000.

Figure 10 shows the live performance with Songrium3D. The centerpiece of the figure of Hatsune Miku on the DILAD screen and the movie generated by Songrium3D shown over her head. At the bottom, one can see the many light sticks swung by audiences members. The live show used the prerecorded singing voice and prerecorded dancing animations of Hatsune Miku. Only the backup band performed live on the stage.

We produced a prerecorded animation of Songrium3D to avert problems deriving from internet connections or real-

time rendering. We captured screenshots of Songrium3D in 29.97 fps and combined them to produce a single movie. The movie of the live performance⁴ and the animation of Songrium3D for the live⁵ are published on the Web.

6.3 Interactive History Player in public events

The Interactive History Player has been used at two big public events, *Nico Nico Chokaigi 3*⁶, *Nico Nico Chokaigi 2015*⁷ and *Magical Mirai 2014 in Osaka*⁸. The first two were public events for Nico Nico hosted by Niwango, Inc. Chokaigi 3 held April 26-27, 2014. The total number of attendees was 124,966. Similarly, Chokaigi 2015 held April 25-26, 2015 and the total number of attendees was 151,115 that is up 20% over last year. The last one was a public event for Hatsune Miku hosted by Crypton Future Media, Inc. It was held in August 30, 2014 and the total number of attendees is about 11,000.

Figure 11 presents the appearance of the system in each event. Many people enjoyed using the Interactive History Player and watched videos nostalgically. At first many people were passively browsing contents using the system, and then they seek their own memorial contents or period using the category filtering and the time warp function. Some users talked about good old contents with friends while using our system.

7. RELATED WORK

Songrium, at its core, is a music browsing assistance service. Most previous research into interactive music browsing has emphasized visualization to explore musical collections. Given the multiple dimensions associated with

⁴ <https://youtu.be/GOano9x9cBY>

⁵ <https://youtu.be/71o8Jit1c4I>

⁶ <http://www.chokaigi.jp/2014/abroadEnglish.html>

⁷ <http://www.chokaigi.jp/2015/abroadEnglish.html>

⁸ <http://magicalmirai.com/2014/index.en.html>

Figure 7. Transition from top page to a user-specified song in Songrium3D. All original VOCALOID songs are visualized in a three-dimensional space. The colors of these stars correspond to VOCALOID characters, with brightness indicating popularity (number of plays).

music data, a particular visualization technique that is often attempted is visualization of a music collection in a two-dimensional plane [7–9] and three-dimensional plane [10–13]. Our Music Star Map (see Section 3.3) and Songrium3D (see Section 4) are particular examples of this. Interactive interfaces are also important for user experiences; [14] assists a user in discovering songs. [15] assists a user in finding artists. In contrast to the advances in interactive music browsing described above, Songrium visualizes not only original songs, but also their derivative works and respective histories, facilitating the effortless browsing of web-native musical content. Furthermore, we apply our visualization methods to huge and dynamic music content and release them as a web application.

Music recommendation [16–18] is an automated method to give users the opportunity to encounter unfamiliar but potentially interesting songs. Similarly, automatic playlist generation [19–22] can provide such opportunities for users. Songrium also assists such user activities by visualizing massive user-generated music content. However, Celma reports the collaborative filtering approach which is a typical recommendation method that is prone to popularity bias [23]. It means that a tendency by which “The rich get richer” is reinforced by music recommendations. It is unsuitable for a browsing assistance of massive user-generated music content, but Kamalzadeh reports 50% of active listeners would like to choose songs one after another [24]. Furthermore, just 9% use online recommen-

Figure 8. Examples of pair of visual effects and repeated sections. Each visual effects is mapped to chorus section or one repeated section. In the left one, the current time is in repeated section 1 and 2. Then users can see a mix of visual effects 1 and 2. Each visual effects will be started at the beginning of the repeated section.

Figure 10. Songrium3D on the live stage of Hatsune Miku. Animation generated by Songrium3D is shown in the gate-shaped LED display.

dation and 10% use shuffle when listening to a collection. This result indicates that active listeners enjoy not only listening to songs but also choosing songs. Regarding this point, visualizing massive user-generated music content can provide an excellent experience for active listeners, having a complementary relation with music recommendation.

8. CONCLUSIONS

As described in this paper, we proposed two new interfaces of a music browsing assistance service called *Songrium* that visualizes *VOCALOID* music including original songs and their derivative works on the video sharing site *Niconico*. Our target music content was *web-native music*: music content that was born, listened to, and distributed on the web. *Songrium* provides various visualization tools

Figure 11. Demonstration of Interactive History Player in public event. The left photograph shows that a child used our system with touch panel display at public event for Niconico. The right photograph shows the booth of our demonstration at public event for Hatsune Miku.

to assist users in grasping the relations among web-native music. In particular, this paper features *Songrium3D* that shows whole of web-native music content in a community and *Interactive History Player* that presents a history of web-native music content.⁹

For future work, we will continue to run the Songrium service and improve it based on user feedback. Herein, we described only VOCALOID music, but web-native music is available from many other sources, which we hope to exploit in the near future.

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